

Notes

Copper (II) and Nickel (II) Complexes of Neutral Bidentate Schiff Base

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IN continuation of our previous work on the nickel (II) and copper (II) complexes of neutral Schiff bases,^{1,2} we have further isolated some copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes of the neutral bidentate Schiff base ligands derived by the condensation of ethylenediamine with acetophenone (abbreviated as BAPE) and benzaldehyde (abbreviated as BBE). This note describes the preparation and properties of these complexes of copper (II) and nickel (II).

Experimental

Solvent purification, electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurement, elemental analyses, and the record of infrared spectral data were done as described previously.¹⁻³

Preparation of copper (II) complexes, $Cu(BAPE)_2X_2$ (where, $X=NO_3^-, ClO_4^-, \frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}$: All thereactions were done in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The same general procedure was followed to prepare the different copper (II) chelates.

Copper (II) salt (0.005 mole) (nitrate, perchlorate, or sulphate) was boiled (~ 15 minutes) in 25 ml. of 2,2-dimethoxypropane and then added to a solution of BAPE^{1,2} (0.01 mole) in 30 ml. of *n*-butylalcohol. The mixture was refluxed for 30 minutes and then filtered. The filtrate, on concentration under reduced pressure, gave bright green or green crystals, which were filtered off and washed with dry diethylether and ultimately dried in vacuo.

$[Cu(BAPE)_2](NO_3)_2$ (I): Bright green crystals. Found: Cu, 9.08%; N, 11.85%; $\mu_{eff}=2.00$ (at 302°K); ν_{max} (in 1,2-dichloroethane), 14,320 cm^{-1} (broad). Calc for (I): Cu, 8.88%; N, 11.74%.

$[Cu(BAPE)_2](ClO_4)_2$ (II): Green crystals. Found: Cu, 7.90%; N, 6.82%; $\mu_{eff}=2.18$ (at 300°K); ν_{max} (in 1,2 dichloroethane), 14,350 cm^{-1} (broad). Calc for (II): Cu, 8.03%; N, 7.04%.

$[Cu(BAPE)_2]SO_4$ (III): Green crystals. Found: Cu, 9.00%; N, 8.53%; $\mu_{eff}=2.05$ (at 300°K); ν_{max} (in 1,2-dichloroethane), 14,348 cm^{-1} (broad) Calc for (III): Cu, 9.24%; N, 8.14%.

Preparation of nickel (II) complexes, $Ni(APE)(SCN)_2$ and $Ni(BBE)(SCN)_2$ (where, $APE=C_6H_5(CH_2)_3C=NCH_2CH_2NH_2$): Ethanolic solution of nickel (II) nitrate hexahydrate (0.005 mole) and potassium thiocyanate (0.01 mole) were mixed and the precipitated potassium nitrate was filtered off

and rejected. The filtrate was somewhat concentrated by slow evaporation in a water-bath and to this concentrated solution was then added the solution of BAPE (0.015 mole) in ethanol. The bluish green compound appeared changed immediately to a light green crystalline compound. This was filtered off, washed with ethanol and ether, and dried in vacuo. The compound $Ni(APE)(SCN)_2$ is not appreciably soluble in ordinary organic solvents, except the coordinating one.

Analogous procedure using BBE (prepared *in-situ* by refluxing benzaldehyde and ethylenediamine) instead of BAPE yielded a green crystalline complex, $Ni(BBE)(SCN)_2$. This was washed with alcohol and ether and dried in vacuo. The complex is not soluble in ordinary organic solvents, except the coordinating one.

$Ni(APE)(SCN)_2$ (IV): Light green crystal. Found: Ni, 17.95%; SCN, 36.01%; $\mu_{eff}=3.02$ (at 303°K); ν_{max} (nujol mull), 10,800, 13,500 (sh), 16,900 cm^{-1} ; Calc for (IV): Ni, 18.05%; SCN, 35.99%.

$Ni(BBE)(SCN)_2$ (V): Green crystal. Found: Ni, 14.28%; SCN, 28.50%; $\mu_{eff}=3.25$ (at 303°K); ν_{max} (nujol mull), 11,000, 13,500 (sh), 17,000 cm^{-1} . Calc for (V): Ni, 14.15%; SCN, 28.30%.

Results and Discussion

Copper (II) complexes: These compounds are moisture sensitive. The elemental analyses support the formulation $Cu(BAPE)_2X_2$ ($X=NO_3^-, ClO_4^-$ or $\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}$) for the complexes, and are paramagnetic with effective magnetic moments ranging from 2.00-2.18 B.M. at room temperature. Although these moment values are quite close to the value (2.2 B.M. at room temperature) prescribed for tetrahedral copper (II) complexes^{4,5}, yet the room temperature magnetic moment is not sufficient to assign structure for a copper (II) complex.

The electronic spectra of the complexes in 1,2-dichloroethane show a broad band around 14,350 cm^{-1} . Regular tetrahedral copper (II) complexes are expected to give a single broad band in the near infrared ($\epsilon \sim 10^2$) and to have no absorption between 10,000 and 20,000 cm^{-1} . As distortion towards square planar geometry increases, the bands in the near infrared of tetrahedral copper (II) are expected to move towards higher frequency, i e., towards previously transparent 10,000 to 20,000 cm^{-1} region⁶. It is thus possible that the copper (II) complexes $Cu(BAPE)_2X_2$ may attain a flattened tetrahedral geometry. This is purely a tentative assignment, as one would need to examine the spectral bands below 10,000 cm^{-1} range for a more meaningful interpretation of the spectral data. Laboratory limitation does not allow us to do so.

The infrared spectral data show that the nitrate, perchlorate, and sulphate groups are present as free anions in the complexes (I) to (III). The complex $Cu(BAPE)_2(NO_3)_2$ (I) shows two weak bands at 825 and 710 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned as ν_2 and ν_4 modes of vibrations respectively of the free NO_3 ion

(in D_{3h} symmetry)⁷⁻⁹. A strong band at 1395 cm^{-1} observed in the above nitrocomplex (I) may be assigned as ν_3 mode of vibration of ionic nitro group. In $\text{Cu}(\text{BAPE})_2\text{SO}_4$ (III) two strong i.r. bands are observed at 1122 cm^{-1} (ν_3) and 619 cm^{-1} (ν_4), which suggests that the T_d symmetry of the SO_4^{2-} still holds¹⁰ in the complex. Again, the strong band observed at 1098 cm^{-1} in the complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{BAPE})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (II), may be considered ν_3 mode of vibration in free ClO_4^- ion in T_d symmetry.^{11,12}

Nickel (II) complexes : The reaction of $\text{Ni}(\text{SCN})_2$ with BAPE yields $\text{Ni}(\text{APE})(\text{SCN})_2$ (IV) instead of

We are not sure whether the initially formed unstable bluish green complex contain BAPE.

obvious that one azomethine bond is hydrolysed to yield the complex (IV). Although the insolubility of the complex suggests the polymeric nature of the complex; we are unable to provide any proof at this moment about polymerization. The reaction of BBE with $\text{Ni}(\text{SCN})_2$ also produced an insoluble complex $\text{Ni}(\text{BBE})(\text{SCN})_2$ (V), possibly polymeric in nature.

The observed μ_{eff} values for nickel (II) complexes (IV) and (V) is 3.02 and 3.29 B.M. respectively, which is in excellent agreement with the predicted magnetic moments for octahedral nickel (II) complexes.¹³⁻¹⁶ This geometry for the present nickel (II) complexes (IV) and (V) has also been substantiated by the electronic spectra of the complexes in nujol mull, although the spectral bands suggest much distortion from the idealized O_h point symmetry¹⁷.

The infrared spectrum of the complex $\text{Ni}(\text{APE})(\text{SCN})_2$ (IV) shows three bands at $3368(\text{s})\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu_{as}\text{NH}$), $3200(\text{br, s})\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu_s\text{NH}$), and $1602(\text{s})\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (δNH). It reveals that in the complex (IV) the ligand APE contains a $-\text{NH}_2$ group which is coordinated to the metal ion. On the other hand, the complex $\text{Ni}(\text{BBE})(\text{SCN})_2$ (V) does not show any band for ν_{NH} or δNH . However, the $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ band appears around 1625 cm^{-1} for both the complexes. In the complexes (IV) and (V), three absorption bands appear at: ν_{CN} at $2140-2115\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_1), ν_{CS} at $780-778\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_3), and δNCS at $480-460\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_2) regions. These assignments are made on the basis of previously published work.¹⁸⁻²⁴ The ν_1 and ν_2 bands are split into two peaks mainly in the form of shoulders, which is assignable to the bridging nature of NCS group (s) in the present complexes.¹⁸⁻²⁴ The position of ν_{as} band (as mentioned above) suggests the presence of N -bonded NCS ligand in these chelates. The appearance of multiple bands of medium intensity at $\text{Ca. } 475\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to δNCS vibration of N -bonded, bridged thiocyanate.^{20,23,25}

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Occurrence of $\Delta^{5,25}$ -Stigmastadien-3 β -ol and Erythrodiol in *Pristimera grahamii*

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THE isolation of dulcitol and occurrence of Pristimerin an antibacterial principle, in the root bark of *Pristimera grahamii* has been reported¹⁻⁴. The present investigation deals with the isolation and characterisation of $\Delta^{5,25}$ -stigmastadien-3 β -ol and erythrodiol in the leaves of this plant. The 95% ethanolic Soxhlet extract of air-dried powdered leaves